

Research proposal Statement of Interest

Question to be addressed:

Role of FGF-2 and Churchill in neuron regeneration and its possible use in development of cell replacement therapy for treatment of neuronal degeneration.

Background:

Many neuronal malfunctions are attributed to neurodegeneracy. Many approaches are being considered to understand the development of neurons and steps involved in its differentiation. Embryonal stem cells, neuronal stem cells and hematopoietic stem cells are viewed as a possible source for inducing differentiation into adult neurons. If achieved then it can be used as core of cell replacement therapy.

Studies have shown that various transcription factors have role in neural differentiation and are used while culturing. Out of them FGF-2 is most widely used along with BDNF and certain neurotrophins. One of these **Churchill (churc), a Zinc finger protein is not extensively studied** for its role in dedifferentiation of adult neurons, embryonic stem cells, and hematopoietic stem cells, but has a great role in neural development. This **upregulates early neural genes** for neural differentiation during embryonic development. Its activity is mediated by a **Smad-interacting protein (Sip1)**. Sip1 plays an important role in decision between neural ectoderm in human ESC. Similarly Zic 1 and Zic 3, Irx genes, Fox D4 also play important role in neural differentiation. (1)

Timings and effectiveness of these factors in both embryo and stem cell cultures may be *in vivo* as well may reveal **how to drive cell towards a stabilized neural fate**. (1)

My approach towards the regeneration of neurons is to use promote the differentiation of stem cells *in vitro* and *in vivo* and to check whether factors such as FGF-2 and Churc can be used *directly for* treatment rather than cell replacement therapy.

Experiments planned:

Experiment 1: Isolation of embryonic stem cells, hematopoietic stem cells for *in vitro* studies

- Embryonic stem cells will be isolated from developing embryos
- Hematopoietic stem cells will be isolated from bone marrow of femur

Experiment 2: Culturing of isolated cells and their neuronal conversion in presence of FGF-2 and /or Churc

All these will be cultured in B27/ Neuro-basal media or chemical defined media (2).

To assess the role of **FGF 2** signaling and the role of **Zinc-finger protein Churchill (churc)**, these media are supplemented with these factors.

Setups devised:

- Cultures without any additional transcription factors (control)
- Cultures with FGF only
- Cultures with Churc only
- Cultures with both FGF and Churc protein

The new neurons formed can be checked by taking cell density at various intervals and also by tracking the cell surface biomarkers such as Sox1 for embryonic cell stages and by BrdU labelling/ GFAP/ Neuro D for developing neurons (3).

Experiment 3: *in vivo* Study of neuronal differentiation

For *in vivo* studies, the neuronal differentiation factors (FGF and Churc) along with enriched preparation of stem cells will be injected at specific sites and their effect will be studied. For this experimental set up will be devised based on the results from experiment-2.

Sites for injecting these factors will be: Sub-ventricular zone (SVZ) of hippocampus, olfactory bulb, parts of spinal cord, parts of cerebrum, and cerebellum.

The effect of these factors and regeneration of new neurons can be assayed using immunohistochemistry, retrograde labelling, and electrophysiology (4). Further these mice can be put to tests used to diagnose the degeneration. And if diagnosis is absent then it suggests positive result.

Expected outcomes and Alternatives:

1. Neuronal differentiation should occur in all the experiments. It should also provide clues into possible roles of FGF and Churchill protein that can be utilized for the regeneration of **degenerating neurons**.
2. Successful transdifferentiation of HSC into neurons will give a better option of cell replacement therapy.

Alternatives:

- Studying the role of degenerating neurons in checking the differentiation of stem cells in new neurons.
- Studying the effect of Immune system factors at the site of inflammation due to degenerating neurons on regeneration of new neurons.

References:

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2. Gregory J. Brewer. Regeneration and Proliferation of Embryonic and adult Rat Hippocampal Neurons in Culture. *Experimental Neurology*. 1999; 159: 237- 247.
3. Zhang J., Jiao J. Molecular Biomarkers for Embryonic and Adult Neural Stem Cell and Neurogenesis. *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology*. 2015
4. Sigurjonsson E. O., Perreault C.M., Egeland T., Glover C. J. Adult Hematopoietic Stem Cell produce Neurons Efficiently in the Regenerating Chick Embryo Spinal Cord. *PNAS*. 2005; 102: 5227-5232